

Measurement of nuclear effects via final-state correlations in quasielastic-like events on hydrocarbon at MINERvA

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Introduction

A good understanding of nuclear effects in neutrino interactions is crucial for neutrino oscillation experiments. These effects, such as initial state Fermi motion and final interactions are challenging to measure

New observables are measured at the MINERvA experiment using transverse kinematic imbalances¹ and neutron momentum² in quasielastic-like interactions to study nuclear effects

MINERvA Experiment

Fine-grained scintillator tracker surrounded by calorimeters

MINERvA uses MINOS Near Detector which serves as a magnetized muon spectrometer

The neutrino flux for the data presented here uses data collected between March 2010 and April 2012 (Low Energy)

An ongoing analysis using the Medium Energy in the solid targets: carbon, iron, lead and water

Signal and Selection

Signal definition: CCQE-like events

- One muon and at least one proton, no mesons
- Muon and proton kinematics as follows:

$$1.5 \text{ GeV}/c < p_\mu < 10 \text{ GeV}/c, \theta_\mu < 20^\circ,$$

$$0.45 \text{ GeV}/c < p_p < 1.2 \text{ GeV}/c, \theta_p < 70^\circ$$

Event Selection:

- Muon candidate tracked into muon spectrometer (MINOS)
- Identify proton candidate(s) using using dE/dx along track
- Elastically scattered contained proton³
- Remove pions using a Michel electron tag
- Cut on energy far from vertex (unattached visible energy) to remove events with untracked pions

References

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- 2 A.Furmanski, J. Sobczyk, Phys. Rev. C95 (2017) no6, 065501
- 3 X. Lu, M. Betancourt, arXiv:1608.04655
- 4 Callum Wilkinson, et al., Phys. Rev. C70(2004) 055503
- 5 Nieves et al., Phys. Rev. D90 (2014) no11, 1120017 Phys. Rev. C 86, 015504 (2012)

Initial Neutron Momentum and Transverse Kinematic Imbalances

The initial and final state nuclear effects are probed using the momentum of the struck neutron and the direction of the μ -p transverse momentum imbalance are measured

Differential cross section in initial struck neutron momentum P_n

The initial neutron momentum is reconstructed using the kinematics of the quasielastic-like events

$$\text{Transverse} \quad 0 = \vec{p}_T^{\ell'} + \vec{p}_T^{N'} - \delta\vec{p}_T$$

$$\text{Longitudinal} \quad E_\nu = p_L^{\ell'} + p_L^{N'} - \delta p_L$$

$$\text{New variable} \quad p_n \equiv \sqrt{\delta p_T^2 + \delta p_L^2}$$

Data is compared with **MnvGENIE-v1***:

- The dashed curve is the pure QE without FSI; distribution shows the QE peak and Bodek-Richie tail
- Non-exclusive: RES, DIS+Other and 2p2h are separated from QE peak due to large intra-nuclear momentum transfer

The deficit at $P_n \sim 0.3 \text{ GeV}/c$ could be lacking strength on 2p2h

Differential cross section in transverse boosting angle, $\delta\alpha_T$

The transverse boosting angle, $\delta\alpha_T$ represents the direction of the transverse momentum imbalance

$$\delta\vec{p}_T \equiv \vec{p}_T^{\ell'} + \vec{p}_T^{N'}$$

$$\delta\alpha_T \equiv \arccos \frac{-\vec{p}_T^{\ell'} \cdot \delta\vec{p}_T}{p_T^{\ell'} \delta p_T}$$

For the simulation without FSI, the distribution of $\delta\alpha_T$ is flat

Effects of the final state interactions are shown at $\delta\alpha_T > 90$ degrees

The overall MnvGENIE-v1 prediction describes the $\delta\alpha_T$ distribution well

Data Compared with NuWro

NuWro simulation is compared with data separately using the Local Fermi Gas model and the Spectral Function

The prediction for P_n with Spectral function describes the data much better than LFG, but more strength is needed at $P_n \sim 0.3 \text{ GeV}/c$

Summary

The first cross sections of quasielastic-like in terms of P_n and $\delta\alpha_T$ are reported. The target Fermi motion and the intranuclear momentum transfer are separated with these new observables. We find a better agreement between data and GENIE simulation when 2p2h is simulated. We find MnvGENIE-v1 and NuWro with Spectral Function provide good descriptions of the single particle kinematics and reasonable predictions for P_n and $\delta\alpha_T$. However, both generators fail in the transition region between Fermi motion and intranuclear momentum transfer.